

Microbial degradation of polyhydroxy ether of bisphenol-A using pseudomonous species

Samaresh Ghosh^a, Ajit K. Banthia^{a*}, Swagata Dasgupta^b and Rintu Banerjee^c

^aMaterials Science Centre, ^bDepartment of Chemistry, ^cDepartment of Agriculture and Food Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur-721 302, India

E-mail : abanthia@hotmail.com Fax : 91-3222-755303

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Degradation of polyhydroxy ether of bisphenol-A (PHEBA) by cultured microorganisms has been studied by isolating soil microbe, identified as pseudomonous species. The extent of degradation of the polymer films was determined by monitoring the percent weight-loss, change in intrinsic viscosity, as well as chemical change using IR spectroscopy at different intervals of time.

In our effort¹, we studied the microbial susceptibility of PHEBA incorporating ester linkages into the main chain by soil burial method. However, there is no known microbial stain which can degrade the aromatic ether linkages present in the polymeric main chain, like epoxy resin, polyhydroxy ether etc. Therefore, we report herein the microbial susceptibility of PHEBA by cultured microorganisms, isolated from soil and identified as pseudomonous species. The degradation by soil microorganisms has also been studied and estimated from percent weight-loss², change in intrinsic viscosity³ as well as some chemical changes by using IR spectroscopy⁴.

Results and discussion

PHEBA was synthesized by the reaction of diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A and bisphenol-A as reported earlier¹. The intrinsic viscosity of yellowish-white PHEBA was found to be 0.179 dl/g, measured in CHCl₃ at 36 ± 0.1°.

Each of the degrading films was checked for transparency and brittleness at various stages of the test. They become embrittled and non-transparent as the test continued. The gradual embrittlement of the polymer films is indicative of strong microbial attack. The primary measure of degradation was weight-loss under controlled conditions. The significant change of polymer film was monitored by percent weight-loss and intrinsic viscosity change (Fig. 1) at different incubation times at 32°. The intrinsic viscosity is a

Fig. 1. Degradation profile of PHEBA polymer in the presence of pseudomonous species : (I) percent weight-loss vs incubation time and (Δ) intrinsic viscosity vs incubation time.

measure of molecular weight. The extent of degradation at the initial stage increases, then levels off upto a certain period. After this period the extent of degradation becomes rapid. At the initial stage, the preferential degradation of relatively low molecular weight polymer molecules takes place due to their greater accessibility to the enzyme system of soil microbe. However, after this initial stage, there is only a marginal increase in the extent of degradation as the molecules of low molecular weight are consumed by this time. This may be attributed to the presence of majority of relatively high molecular weight molecules at that time creating difficulty in entering into the microbial cell. There are some literature references⁵ to the decrease in biodegradability with increasing molecular weight of the polymer. After the

second stage, the extent of degradation increases again due to decrease in molecular weight which leads to an increased vulnerability to biological attack as evidenced from Fig. 1. However, from the trend of the degradation of this polymer, it is evident that the addition of low molecular weight species of the same polymer helps the growth of microorganisms with considerable metabolic activities which may subsequently decay the high molecular weight chains also. There was no significant change in IR spectra except the region 3675–3350 cm^{-1} of the polymer. The spectral appearance of this polymer, incubated with pseudomonous species, indicates the non-appearance of new functional group. The IR spectrum of the original polymer shows both the H-bonded and free O-H stretching at 3395 and 3510 cm^{-1} , respectively. These diagnostic bands appear as a single broad band at 3370 cm^{-1} with advancement of incubation time.

It can be concluded that the addition of low molecular weight species of the same polymer helps the growth of microorganisms with considerable metabolic activities which may subsequently decay the high molecular weight chains also.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Sodium nitrate (SD), potassium chloride (SD), magnesium sulfate (E. Merck), potassium dihydrogen phosphate (E. Merck) were used as received.

Viscosity was measured in chloroform using a Ubbelohde viscometer thermostated at $(36 \pm 0.1)^\circ$. The intrinsic viscosities $[\eta]$ of the polymers were determined by using the equation⁶,

$$\log [\eta] = \log \left[\frac{(\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1)/C}{\log(\eta_{\text{sp}}/C) - K\eta_{\text{ref}}} \right] - K[\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1]$$

where C is the concentration (g/dl). The equation shows good fit when $K = 0.14$ for $(\eta_{\text{rel}} - 1) < 0.3$.

Films of the polymer sample were prepared by conventional solvent-casting techniques from chloroform solution of the polymer (~11%) using glass plate as casting surfaces. The solution cast films were then kept for slow solvent evaporation at room temperature and then dried under vacuum to constant weight. The film was then cut into several pieces with a particular specification for testing of biodegradation.

Microbial degradation with cultured microorganisms⁷:

Microorganisms were isolated⁸ from the local soil of IIT campus, Kharagpur. The nutrient medium, used for the isolation of microorganisms, was sufficient to supply

nitrogen and the trace element sources, but specifically maintained free of any traces of carbon sources. As a carbon source, this medium was supplemented with polymer films. By this way, the microbial species, growing and propagating in the nutrient medium (Czapek dox) where the only carbon source was the added polymer film, were considered to be capable of existing on a diet of this polymer as the sole carbon source. The microbial species, potentially capable of utilizing (or mutating and thus assimilating) the polymers, were then identified as pseudomonous species.

The nutrient medium (Czapek dox⁹) selected had the following composition : NaNO_3 2.5 g dm^{-3} , KCl 0.5 g dm^{-3} , MgSO_4 0.5 g dm^{-3} , KH_2PO_4 1 g dm^{-3} , $\text{pH} = 5.5$.

Degradation procedure :

Polymer pieces (20 mm \times 15 mm) and nutrient solution (Czapek dox; 20 ml) were taken in a conical flask and inoculated aseptically with the isolated microbial inoculum (1 ml in each flask) and kept in the humidifier for several weeks at 32°, 93% relative humidity and 5.5 pH. After incubation, each of the flasks containing polymer pieces were taken out at periodical intervals. Each of the polymer pieces was then recovered by washing of the nutrient medium and microorganisms and finally dried in vacuum to constant weight. The degradation was measured in terms of weight-loss and the change in intrinsic viscosity. Nonmicrobial sterile flasks were also prepared for comparison. These distinguish nonmicrobial degradation from the truly microbe mediated effects.

References

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